

Rest-Activity Rhythms During Clinical Episodes of Bipolar Disorder: Disruptions in Mean Levels, Temporal Variability, and Multivariate Structure

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Abstract. Mood episodes in bipolar disorders (BD) are typically associated with changes in sleep and activity patterns. In this study, we present a novel correlation-based approach to examine the structure of relationships between actigraphy-derived variables and clinical status in individuals with BD. Using a large-scale longitudinal study spanning over 2 years of actigraphic recordings from 115 patients with bipolar disorder (BD), we compared three aggregation approaches: mean values, temporal variability, and inter-feature correlation structure, to classify mood states in a strict validation scenario and predict future episodes. Two binary classification subsets (mania–remission and depression–remission) were constructed based on automatically classified labels using clinician-rated scales (Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale and Young Mania Rating Scale) and weekly self-assessments. Support Vector Machine models with Radial Basis Function kernels were trained using 7-day windows and forward feature selection in a nested 5-fold cross-validation setup. The classification model achieved statistically significant balanced accuracy: 58% ($p < 0.05$) for mania–remission and 59% ($p < 0.001$) for depression–remission. For mania, the most predictive aggregates were shorter mean sleep duration and deviations in 10-hour peak activity across different weeks, while for depression, increased inter-daily variability and intra-daily activity fluctuations emerged as key indicators. The models differentiated future episodes from remission solely from actigraphy data with above-chance accuracy, revealing distinct behavioral signatures for mania and depression. While structural changes in correlation patterns between features differed across mood states, they did not outperform mean or variability-based metrics in classification performance. However, the modest classification performance and high inter-individual variability suggest that personalized modeling approaches may be essential for clinically meaningful prediction. Notably, inter- and intra-weekly feature changes provided the strongest predictive signals, suggesting that straightforward alterations in rest-activity rhythms may better reflect clinical episodes than more complex structural metrics.

Keywords: bipolar disorder, machine learning, long-term study, rest-activity rhythms, actigraphy, mean, variability, correlation.

Key strengths

- We present the first study to evaluate the predictive power of mean levels, temporal variability, and mutual relationships of actigraphic features in the detection of clinical episodes in BD.
- The method is evaluated in a strict validation scenario of predicting future episodes on one of the largest longitudinal actigraphic datasets available in BD, including 115 patients, followed up for more than two years.
- Our results indicate that while the mutual relationships of actigraphic features within weekly windows differ between clinical episodes and remission, these correlation-based patterns are not stronger predictors of clinical status than the mean levels—or even the temporal variability—of the same features.
- Pronounced intra-individual and inter-individual variability in sleep–activity patterns limit the accuracy of existing approaches, highlighting the need for individualized modeling strategies.

Introduction

Bipolar Disorder

The clinical course of Bipolar Disorder (BD) is characterized by mood episodes associated with changes in energy and activity, as well as disruptions of circadian rhythms (Scott, Murray, et al., 2017; Tazawa et al., 2019). Such features, monitored with wrist-worn accelerometers, can help assess activity patterns in different phases of the illness.

Rest-Activity Findings in Patients with BD

Actigraphy is a validated tool to assess motor activity and rest-activity rhythms objectively (Ancoli-Israel et al., 2015), widely applied also to psychiatric studies. However, several reviews have highlighted that, in BD research, its use has mostly focused on studying sleep patterns (Geoffroy et al., 2015; Crescenzo, Economou, Sharpley, Gormez, & Quested, 2017; Scott, Murray, et al., 2017).

Studies examining sleep and rest-activity rhythms using 24-hour actigraphy have identified significant differences not only between individuals with BD and healthy controls or other comparison groups (Harvey, Schmidt, Scarnà, Semler, & Goodwin, 2005; Jones, Hare, & Evershed, 2005; St-Amand, Provencher, Bélanger, & Morin, 2013; Schneider et al., 2022), but also between different clinical states, such as euthymic, depressive, and manic phases (Salvatore et al., 2008; Robillard et al., 2013; Gonzalez, Tamminga, Tohen, & Suppes, 2014). Other interesting differences were observed between individuals with BD and their relatives without BD (Harvey et al., 2005; Jones et al., 2005), as well as between depression cases with and without a family history of BD (Gonzalez et al., 2014; McGlinchey, Gershon, Eidelman, Kaplan, & Harvey, 2014).

In general, individuals with BD tend to have lower motor activity, including reduced peak activity, compared to healthy controls (Janney et al., 2014; Gonçalves, Adamowicz, Louzada, Moreno, & Araujo, 2015). Mood instability in BD is associated with increased fragmentation of activity profiles within and across days, resulting in increased variability in actigraphic features (Kaufmann et al., 2018; Schneider et al., 2022).

During mania, patients show increased variability and complexity in psychomotor activity patterns compared to healthy individuals (Scott, Murray, et al., 2017; Panchal et al., 2022). Conversely, during depressive states, there is a lower average level of motor activity, longer sleep onset

and duration, and simpler activity patterns (lower variability and complexity) compared to healthy controls, as well as a lower average activity level compared to the manic state.

Furthermore, patients with depression show a mostly decreasing trend in motor activity over the course of the episode, while patients with mania show mainly an increasing trend (Krane-Gartiser et al., 2017; Panchal et al., 2022; Kaplan, Talbot, Gruber, & Harvey, 2012; Krane-Gartiser, Henriksen, Morken, Vaaler, & Fasmer, 2014; Scott, Vaaler, Fasmer, Morken, & Krane-Gartiser, 2017). Compared to healthy controls, patients in manic episodes have significantly longer sleep latency, longer wake time after sleep onset, and reduced sleep quality (Jakobsen et al., 2022), as well as varied daily activity profiles with an earlier activity onset (Zhang et al., 2023).

The reduction in sleep quality in BD is reflected by increased motor activity and prolonged wakefulness during nighttime sleep (Scott, 2011). The assumption of longer and more variable sleep duration in BD is supported by some studies (Millar, Espie, & Scott, 2004; Ritter et al., 2012; Schneider et al., 2022), although conflicting findings exist (Kaplan et al., 2012; St-Amand et al., 2013). Longer sleep latency in patients with BD can be manifested by reduced pre-sleep activity and increased activity after sleep onset, leading to greater variability in both sleep latency and restlessness and reduced accuracy of actigraphy-based sleep detection (Millar et al., 2004; Ritter et al., 2012; Geoffroy et al., 2014).

Aims of This Study

Previous studies have shown significant but heterogeneous associations between actigraphic parameters and clinical states: both in terms of shifts in mean values, as well as changes in temporal variability (Krane-Gartiser et al., 2014, 2017; Jakobsen et al., 2024). Furthermore, changes in the mutual structure of actigraphic features have not been studied; For example, longer sleep duration may correlate with lower daily activity in remission (due to shorter wakeful day) but not in mania (due to fragmented regime and agitation).

This study aims to investigate differences in mean value, temporal variability, and structure of relationships between actigraphic parameters as a function of changes in the patient's clinical status, answering the following research questions:

1. Do the a) mean value, b) temporal variability, and c) structure of relationships between actigraphic features differ between mania–remission and depression–remission, when evaluated

within weekly windows?

2. Which of these three aggregation approaches is the most predictive of symptom changes?

We employ a machine-learning based scenario to evaluate the predictive capacity of the suggested data aggregation approaches, each investigating a separate aspect of motor activity changes during mood episodes in BD.

Data and Methods

Participants and Data

The study data originate from the observational, non-interventional study AKTIBIPO 400 (Anýž et al., 2021). The study included 326 BD patients aged 18 to 65, euthymic at baseline (Montgomery-Åsberg Depression Rating Scale (MADRS) ≤ 15 , Young Mania Rating Scale (YMRS) ≤ 15), monitored for over 2 years using continuous wrist-worn actigraphy (MindG, Mindpax Ltd.) and a digitally administered weekly self-assessment questionnaire Aktibipo Self-rating Ecological Momentary Assessment (ASERT) by Mindpax Ltd. (Anýž et al., 2021) for manic and depressive symptoms. A subgroup of the participants (115 participants) was also monitored using monthly clinician-rated MADRS and YMRS via phone interview.

The study was approved by the NIMH institutional ethical committee (Czech Republic; case number: 101/17). Upon enrollment, all participants signed informed consent, and the study was conducted in compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Definition of Clinical State and Data Annotation

Clinical states were annotated using a rule-based algorithm that combined information from three primary sources: monthly ratings (MADRS, YMRS), weekly self-reported questionnaire ASERT (depressive and manic subscores), and patient health records (PHR), including hospitalization and sick leave data related to affective symptoms.

The classification of episodes was primarily based on MADRS and YMRS. Depression was labeled in a 14-day window where MADRS ≥ 15 or by depression-related PHR (hospitalizations or sick leaves). (Hypo)mania was defined in a 14-day window where YMRS ≥ 13 or by mania-related PHR. For both episode types, the labels were extended to all adjacent weeks where the respective

ASERT subscore or weekly change was above a proprietary threshold. Remission corresponded to MADRS and YMRS < 9 and ASERT depressive score (DS) < 5 , and manic score (MS) < 3 . Short missing data gaps (≤ 11 days) were imputed by the same state if it was consistently present both before and after the gap.

Actigraphy and Daily Features

Throughout the study, we recorded continuous wrist actigraphy data aggregated into 30s epochs, from which we computed a set of 28 daily features. The features included the activity and sleep profiles, as well as the classical nonparametric methods. A full list of actigraphic features computed for this study is provided in the Supplementary Table S1. Due to the character of the study, we ensured that only data for the given day were used. We thus did not consider other commonly used actigraphy features that require data from adjacent days for their computation (e.g., cosinor analysis, interdaily stability, intradaily variability).

Data Split and Preprocessing

We split daily annotated data into two binary classification subsets: mania vs. remission and depression vs. remission. In the mania subset, days labeled as mania included both mania and hypomania to ensure sufficient sample size, whereas in the depression subset, only days labeled as depression were included, as described in the Definition of Clinical State and Data Annotation section.

For each subject, complete clinical episodes were chronologically divided in a 3:2 ratio into training and testing sets, such that earlier episodes were used for training and later episodes for testing. This episode-based split demonstrates within-subject generalization but may limit performance due to inter-subject variability or long-term shifts.

Daily actigraphic features were standardized per subject using the mean and standard deviation (SD) of remission-labeled training data, applied consistently to training and test sets (i.e. using train-set based normalization parameters). To stabilize the variance and make the data distribution more symmetric, a Box-Cox transformation (Box & Cox, 1964) was applied, with the λ parameter estimated on the training set and applied to both sets.

The data flow diagram in the Supplementary Figure S1 summarizes these preprocessing steps and shows patient and day counts at each stage.

Actigraphic Data Weekly Aggregates

We used three aggregation approaches to distinguish between mania/remission and depression/remission: mean-based approach (μ), time-variability-based approach (σ), and Pearson correlation-based approach (ρ). Each aggregation was computed on the 28 daily actigraphic features within a 7-day non-overlapping window, selected to suppress the weekly pattern; see Figure 1 for a better visual understanding. To ensure the reliability of aggregated feature labels, only windows with at least 4 days of consistent clinical labeling were used in the classification analyses (see Classification section below). Figure 2 presents a flowchart illustrating the dataset sizes before and after weekly aggregation.

Fig 1: Aggregation approaches computation

where x and y denote actigraphic features, and i is the day index within the week window.

Visualization of three aggregation approaches for discriminating mania/depression from remission: value-based (μ) using the mean of each feature within a 7-day window; time-variability-based (σ) using within-window standard deviation; and structure-based (ρ) using Pearson correlations between features. Aggregations were computed over $n = 28$ daily actigraphic features in non-overlapping 7-day windows, requiring at least 4 days of data with consistent clinical labels.

Fig 2: Dataset size before and after weekly aggregation

The flow chart shows sizes of the training/test sets for the mania/depression classification subsets before and after weekly aggregation (μ —mean / σ —standard deviation / ρ —Pearson correlation). For details on preprocessing, see Supplementary Figure S1; for classification methodology, see Supplementary Figure S2.

Classification

For the classification model, we used a Support Vector Machine (SVM) with a Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel (Cortes & Vapnik, 1995), uniform class priors, and a kernel scale of 1 (due to standardized input). To address class imbalance, misclassification penalties were adjusted during training.

Each week included 28 daily actigraphic features, yielding 434 weekly aggregates: 28 μ , 28 σ , and 378 ρ . Dimensionality was reduced by removing highly correlated aggregates (> 0.8), followed by forward feature selection (FFS) using 3-fold cross-validation (CV). Within each fold,

a nested 5-fold CV tuned hyperparameters and selected features, optimizing a balanced accuracy (BA)-based criterion that penalized sensitivity–specificity imbalance.

Stable aggregates selected in at least two folds were retained. To further mitigate imbalance, we tuned the false negative (FN) penalty via grid search (range 1.0—3.0, step 0.1), with the false positive (FP) penalty fixed at 1. The final model was retrained on the complete training set using the stable aggregates and evaluated on the held-out test set.

An overview of the model training and evaluation is shown in Supplementary Figure S2.

Evaluation and Statistical Analysis

To assess model performance on imbalanced data, we used sensitivity (SENS), specificity (SPEC), and BA, the latter being more reliable than standard accuracy under class imbalance.

A permutation test with 10,000 label shuffles was used to generate a null distribution of BA. The p-value was computed as the proportion of permuted BA values exceeding the observed BA, and significance was determined at $\alpha = 0.05$.

To interpret actigraphic features across clinical states, we computed standardized mean difference (SMD) and 95% confidence interval (CI) in the training set, using pooled SD.

All analyses were performed in MATLAB (R2023b) (The MathWorks, Inc., 2023).

Results

Participants and Data

Following preprocessing, dataset splitting, and weekly aggregation of actigraphic recordings, we derived a structured dataset for subsequent classification analyses. The initial cohort consisted of 326 participants with bipolar disorder, out of which the monthly MADRS and YMRS clinician ratings were available for 115. From them, we selected two analytical subsets: participants with at least one episode of mania and remission ($n = 43$), and those with at least one episode of depression and remission ($n = 65$), totaling 84 unique participants (due to partial overlap), used for actigraphy data processing and normalization. The final set used for classification included data from participants with multiple recorded episodes: 23 participants in the mania subset, contributing 148 weeks labeled as mania and 567 weeks as remission, and 42 participants in the depression subset, contributing 347 weeks labeled as depression and 832 weeks as remission, total 51 unique

participants. The demographic, health, and activity characteristics of the participants included in each subset are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic, health, and activity characteristics of subjects

	Mania subset *	Depression subset
Cohort overview		
Participants (final / original **)	23 / 43	42 / 65
Sex – female	17 (74%)	22 (52%)
Age	34.8 ± 8.6	38.7 ± 9.7
Body Mass Index (BMI)	27.6 ± 6.4	28.9 ± 6.3
Actigraphy available days (per participant)		
Follow up days	1060.0 ± 284.4	988.6 ± 338.1
Mean percentage of valid days †	81.7 ± 11.0	80.8 ± 13.8
Number of weekly ASERT questionnaires (individual counts)		
Number of questionnaires	125.5 ± 33.3	106.8 ± 42.8
Questionnaires per week	1.0 ± 0.2	1.0 ± 0.2
Episode-scoring questionnaires total	2.1 ± 1.7	4.8 ± 2.7
Clinical scales (individual means)		
Baseline MADRS	4.5 ± 5.1	6.6 ± 6.1
Episode MADRS	2.3 ± 2.6	19.6 ± 4.2
Remission MADRS	2.7 ± 1.4	3.3 ± 2.0
Baseline YMRS	3.0 ± 4.0	2.9 ± 4.3
Episode YMRS	14.9 ± 3.1	1.0 ± 1.2
Remission YMRS	2.0 ± 1.1	1.5 ± 1.2
Episode intervention total ‡	21	17
Available episodes per participant (individual min / mean / max)		
Episode periods total	1 / 3.5 / 29	1 / 4.3 / 13
Remission periods total	5 / 16.2 / 35	4 / 16.8 / 35
Used episode weeks	1 / 6.4 / 23	1 / 8.3 / 38
Used remission weeks	1 / 24.7 / 73	1 / 19.8 / 75
Total number of weeks used for classification		
Total number of used episode weeks	148	347
Total number of used remission weeks	567	832

* Includes both manic and hypomanic episodes as defined in the Definition of Clinical State and Data Annotation, and Data Split and Preprocessing section

** Number of participants included pre- and post-aggregation of actigraphic data

† Days with at least 80% of available samples (also excludes non-wear periods)

‡ Defined as the sum of hospitalizations and sick leaves

Periods (= periods of continuous labeling, with no respect to the length of the episode)

Classification Results

The classification results are provided in Table 2. The classification model based purely on aggregated actigraphic data achieved 58% ($p < 0.05$) in distinguishing mania from remission and 59%

($p < 0.001$) BA in distinguishing depression from remission. For the mania subset, the model demonstrated sensitivity of 48% and specificity of 67%. In the depression subset, sensitivity was 55% and specificity was 62%.

Decision boundaries of the Support Vector Machine model with a Radial Basis Function kernel, applied to the training and test sets, are illustrated in Figure 3, with separate visualizations for the mania (Figure 3a) and depression (Figure 3b) subsets.

Table 2: Classification results

(a) Mania subset							
	<i>weeks mania</i>	<i>weeks rem</i>	<i>subjects</i>	<i>SENS</i>	<i>SPEC</i>	<i>BA</i>	<i>p-value</i>
train set	119	409	23	0.73	0.72	0.73	< .001 ***
test set	29	158	9	0.48	0.67	0.58	< .05 *

(b) Depression subset							
	<i>weeks dep</i>	<i>weeks rem</i>	<i>subjects</i>	<i>SENS</i>	<i>SPEC</i>	<i>BA</i>	<i>p-value</i>
train set	240	582	40	0.69	0.68	0.68	< .001 ***
test set	107	250	25	0.55	0.62	0.59	< .001 ***

Classification results for mania (2a) and depression (2b) subsets, including sensitivity (SENS), specificity (SPEC), and balanced accuracy (BA). The p-value of the BA was computed using a permutation test with 10,000 iterations, where the class labels were randomly permuted to generate a null distribution of BA. The p-value represents the proportion of permuted BA values greater than or equal to the observed BA.

Fig 3: Decision boundary visualization

(a) Mania subset

(b) Depression subset

Decision boundaries of the Support Vector Machine model with Radial Basis Kernel function on train- and test-sets for selected weekly actigraphy aggregates (μ —mean and σ —standard deviation) from the mania (3a) and depression (3b) subsets. For the μ aggregates on the x-axis, the episodes (red) are associated with extreme values on both ends, compared to the remission (blue). This contrasts with the simple shifted values during episodes for the actigraphy aggregates shown on the y-axis.

(M10—total activity during the 10 most active hours of the day, daily SD—standard deviation of activity within a calendar day, for more details, see Supplementary Table S1)

Actigraphic Aggregates Selection Results

Figure 4 presents the effect sizes, computed using the SMD, for the actigraphic feature aggregates identified for classification, as outlined in the Classification section. For fold-specific aggregates selection details, see Supplementary Figures S3 and S4.

Fig 4: Predictive power of weekly actigraphic feature aggregates

Effect sizes (standardized mean difference - SMD) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) of the selected actigraphic aggregates for mania (4a) and depression (4b) subsets in all cross-validation (CV) folds. SMD was computed using the mean difference divided by the pooled SD over the entire training set, meaning the values close to zero are closer to the remission values. Aggregates are sorted by effect size and grouped by aggregation approach: mean (μ), standard deviation (σ), and correlation (ρ). The aggregates, selected in at least two out of three folds (orange), were used for the final models, while additional aggregates selected in only one of the three CV folds are in blue. (M10—total activity during the 10 most active hours of the day, L5—total activity during the 5 least active hours of the day, WASO—Wake After Sleep Onset, M10 RMSSD—Root Mean Square of Successive Differences within 10 most active hours each day, sleep RMSSD—Root Mean Square of Successive Differences of activity during the main daily sleep period, daily SD—Standard Deviation of activity within a calendar day, for more details, see Supplementary Table S1)

In the mania classification subset, the most predictive and stable aggregate across the fold was the mean sleep duration during the week ($\mu(\text{sleep duration})$), where shorter sleep durations indicated mania and longer durations corresponded to remission. The second key aggregate, mean

activity in the most active 10-hour window ($\mu(\text{M10})$), showed a different pattern—values near the center (0 after transformation) aligned with remission, while those deviating from the center indicated mania (as shown in Figure 3). While $\mu(\text{M10})$ alone exhibited limited predictive power, its discriminative capacity increased substantially when combined with $\mu(\text{sleep duration})$, as the joint effect delineated a clearer remission boundary—see Figure 3a and Figure 4a.

For depression, the strongest stable predictor was inter-daily variability ($\sigma(\text{M10})$), with lower variability indicating remission and higher values linked to depression. Another important feature was the intra-daily motor activity variability ($\mu(\text{daily SD})$), which, similar to $\mu(\text{M10})$ in the mania subset, showed that values near the center corresponded to remission, while deviations suggested depression. Although $\mu(\text{daily SD})$ had minimal predictive power on its own, its combination with $\sigma(\text{M10})$ refined the decision boundary, making remission classification more precise.

Although ρ aggregates varied by mood state across folds, it did not outperform μ - or σ -based features and was excluded from the final model in both subsets.

Discussion

In this study, we evaluated three possible aggregation approaches to actigraphy data and evaluated their ability to distinguish clinical episodes. We used clinically annotated data from 115 BD patients, followed up using actigraphy for three years, which we divided into two separate subsets to distinguish i) future episodes of mania from remission and ii) future episodes of depression from remission. We evaluated the machine learning models using data from 51 participants for whom multiple subsequent episodes were recorded.

The classification model demonstrated modest but statistically significant accuracy in discriminating different mood states based solely on weekly aggregates of actigraphy data with a similar performance on both subsets. While the accuracy of our classifiers may be lower than some of the recently published results (Lipschitz, Lin, Saghafian, Pike, & Burdick, 2025), there are marked differences in methodology: our study used mood episodes based on clinician-rated MADRS and YMRS scales combined with hospitalization and work incapacity data, which represents a higher level of clinical validity, compared to the self-rating scales used elsewhere. Also, our study uses the classifiers primarily as a means to investigate the predictive capacity of the aggregation approaches - for this purpose, we consider the significant predictive accuracy sufficient.

Alternative classification algorithms, such as gradient boosting, decision trees, random forests, k-nearest neighbors, and neural networks, were also evaluated. None of these approaches substantially outperformed the SVM baseline, nor did they demonstrate consistently inferior performance.

The high variability in performance across CV folds underscores the challenges posed by individual differences and longitudinal effects in the dataset. This variability suggests that personalizing models to account for subject-specific patterns may be a promising direction for future research. Tailored approaches could help mitigate the impact of interindividual differences and enhance the reliability of actigraphy-based mood state classification.

Comparison of the Actigraphy Aggregation Approaches

The predictive ability of the actigraphy aggregation approaches in weekly windows, representing μ -mean values, σ -variability and ρ -relationships between features may be evaluated from the observed effect sizes, as well as frequency with which each feature was selected within the cross-validation folds (Fig 4).

For the mania-remission task, two μ aggregates were consistently selected, with other μ , σ and ρ aggregates showing clinical effects in individual folds. For the depression-remission task, the μ and σ were used for the classification model, while again all types of aggregates showed effects between episodes and remission.

Although ρ aggregates were selected in individual CV folds for both the mania and depression subsets, they were not selected consistently across the majority of folds and therefore were not included in the final model. This suggests that the ρ may convey little additional discriminative power beyond that already captured by μ and σ . Alternatively, the ρ aggregates, each combining two features, may be more susceptible to intra- and inter-individual variability in actigraphy feature values.

Behavioral Insights into Activity Changes during Episodes

During mania, we observed reduced sleep duration ($\mu(\text{sleep duration})$) and altered activity levels ($\mu(\text{M10})$), showing both elevated and diminished activity compared to the remission baseline. In depression, activity became more irregular, as reflected by increased inter-daily variability ($\sigma(\text{M10})$) and intra-daily activity fluctuations ($\mu(\text{daily SD})$). These changes were attributable to

inter-individual differences, even after alignment to individual remission states, and were more prominent in the test set, likely due to distributional differences between training and testing samples.

Our findings align with a subset of studies examining mood-state-specific changes in BD populations (Tazawa et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2023). For example, (Krane-Gartiser et al., 2014) reported lower first-lag autocorrelation and increased high-frequency variance in mania, while depression was associated with lower mean activity and greater variability. Time-of-day differences in activity between mania and depression, particularly in the morning, have also been noted (Krane-Gartiser et al., 2017). Additionally, our results were also consistent with part of the observations reported by (Salvatore et al., 2008), who found that BD patients in manic or mixed episodes exhibited significantly reduced total nocturnal sleep compared to their euthymic state, along with increased daytime sleep.

Although time-of-day features were not consistently selected across cross-validation folds, some folds indicated mood-state-specific morning patterns (see Supplementary Figures S3 and S4). Mania was occasionally associated with increased mean activity and variability post-waking ($\mu(\text{aft wake})$, $\sigma(\text{aft wake})$), while depression was linked to elevated wake after sleep onset ($\mu(\text{WASO})$) and reduced morning-to-noon activity ($\mu(\text{morn2noon})$). These suggest that morning periods may hold clinically relevant information and warrant targeted future research.

Limitations

There are several limitations to be aware of. First, manic episodes are sporadic (Bopp et al., 2010), which made it necessary to include hypomanic states to assemble a reasonably large dataset, despite the study's extended median follow-up duration close to three years on average. Further, the requirement of the selected classification scenario to have multiple episodes of given type as well as multiple remissions may have introduced bias in selecting only patients with an episodic clinical pattern.

We have chosen a weekly window for the computation of the actigraphic aggregates, based on our preliminary explorations. This may have limited the results, as the changes in level, variance, and structure may occur at different time scales, or different time scales may be optimal for different episode types. Due to the lack of evidence on the temporal dynamics of rest-activity rhythm

changes around episode onsets, as well as differences between depressive and manic episodes in that respect, this is an important direction of future research.

The relatively modest classification accuracy—although exceeding chance level—can likely be attributed to the rigorous validation strategy employed. The use of unseen episodes for testing, alongside the longitudinal variability of individual subjects, likely impacted performance.

The inclusion of data collected during the COVID-19 pandemic introduced potential additional variability, although the exploratory data analysis did not show substantial systematic shifts.

Conclusion

On the large-scale longitudinal dataset, the purely actigraphy-based classification model demonstrated promising, but modest, performance in distinguishing between different mood states in unseen future data. The strongest factors distinguishing mania from remission were the reduced mean sleep duration and increased mean activity levels. For depression, the strongest factors were increased variability in activity from day to day and decreased mean activity variability, compared to remission, which is in line with existing literature.

The findings further indicate that the structure of relationships among actigraphy features reflects differences between mania–remission and depression–remission states. However, these structural aggregates did not consistently outperform simpler metrics such as temporal variability and mean values. Thus, while structural changes may offer complementary insights, they were not sufficient on their own to enable fully automated classification of clinical episodes. Moreover, substantial inter-individual variability—despite data alignment efforts—suggests that personalized modeling approaches may be necessary to achieve reliable and clinically useful predictions.

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